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Research Article

**EFFICACY OF CARIES FAMILIARITY IN PRIMARY MOLARS
ON CAVITY FORMATION IN ADJOINING PERMANENT
FIRST MOLAR****¹Dr. Amina Tahir, ²Dr Maria Samraa, ³Dr. Hafiza Rebia Shahid****¹Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital Lahore, ²WMO BHU Bhangi Tehsil Hazro, ³Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital.****Article Received:** October 2020**Accepted:** November 2020**Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: The aim of this research and study was to assess whether the treated and untreated severe early childhood caries (ECC) in primary molars in children would make any impact on the Permanent First Molar (PFM) decays.

Place and duration of study: This current analysis and study was evaluated in Lahore Medical and Dental College, Lahore in duration of one year from 2017 to 2018.

Materials and Methods: For primary molar caries for this project 2,315 boys and 2,153 girls were examined and the time of emergence of permanent first molar, during their primary school time by trained dentist-examiners; at baseline the mean age of the children was 7.1 years.

Results: An affected second primary molar had more effect than a first primary molar. The analyses revealed that girls were more susceptible to caries development; this gender effect was only significant for mandibular molars.

Conclusion: In Light of our exploration and conclusion, which revealed that regardless of treated or not severe ECC had a significant impact on the PFMs, we strongly recommend that the parent of the children experiencing ECC should be informed about the risk of future caries in PFMs.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Amina Tahir,**

Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital Lahore.

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INTRODUCTION:

Clinical and questionnaire data were obtained from a 1-year prospective oral health screening project in Lahore Medical and Dental College, Lahore where 4,468 children were examined annually during their primary school time. This study sought to address the influence of a sound versus affected first and/or second deciduous molar on the incidence of visible caries experience in the adjacent permanent first molar. A multiple survival model allowing for dependent data with possible censoring was applied. The impact of timing of tooth emergence (determining the period at risk), gender, presence of sealants and reported oral hygiene habits was also considered. Cavity formation in permanent first molars was clearly influenced by the status of the adjacent primary molars the effect of the second deciduous molar was most pronounced. Moreover, if both deciduous molars experienced caries and the child presented with poor oral hygiene, a peak in cavity formation of the permanent first molar 1–2 years after emergence was noticed. On the other hand, if a child presented with good oral hygiene, no peak was observed caries risk increased slightly over time. No significant benefit from restoring primary molars could be demonstrated, possibly because of methodological limitations.

The relationship between caries experience in the primary and permanent dentition has been pointed out in many publications [Honkala et al., 1984; [1] Heidmann and Poulsen, 1986 [2]; Greenwell et al., 1990; [3] Raadal and Espelid, 1992; [4] Arrow, 1997 [5] Powell, 1998; [6] Mejare et al., 2001; [7] Vanob bergen et al., 2001; [8] Li and Wang, 2002; [9] Gray et al. [1991]; [10] concluded that caries experience in three or more deciduous molars at the age of 5 was the best predictor of caries experience in the permanent first molars at the age of 7.

In the knowledge that caries is an infectious disease [Caulfield and Griffen, 2000; [11] and that the bulk of caries experience in the deciduous dentition of schoolchildren is situated in the primary molars – teeth that are adjacent to the permanent first molars for about 5–6 years – the question arises what the effect of an affected first and/or second primary molar is on the incidence of visible caries experience in the adjacent permanent first molar. Therefore, the purpose of the present study was to analyze the effect of sound versus decayed and/or restored deciduous molar(s) on the survival of the permanent first molars in the same quadrant. In a previous study in Flemish children multiple survival analyses confirmed the major impact of the status of the deciduous dentition

in addition to occlusal plaque accumulation, reported brushing frequency and gender on the incidence of visible caries experience in permanent first molars [Leroy et al., 2005]. In these analyses, caries experience in the deciduous dentition was assessed at baseline (mean age: 7.1 years) and added to the model as a dichotomous covariate.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**Data Set:**

The data in our evaluation was attained in a cross sectional prospective (2017-2018) oral health screening project in LMDC, Lahore. For this project 2,315 boys and 2,153 girls were examined, during their primary school time by trained dentist-examiners, at baseline the mean age of the children was 7.1 years. The presence of caries was scored visually and recorded (at cavitation level) according to the diagnostic criteria published by the BASCD [Pine et al., 1997]. The presence of plaque on the occlusal surfaces of permanent first molars was assessed using a simplified version of the index described by Carvalho et al. [1989]. [12] At each examination the emergence status of all permanent teeth was recorded. Every individual permanent tooth was scored according to its clinical eruption stage [adapted from Carvalho et al., 1989]. [12] The grades were: P0 = tooth not visible in the mouth; P1 = occlusal surface only partially erupted; P2 = occlusal surface fully erupted, but less than half of the buccal surface erupted; P3 = more than half of the buccal surface erupted, no antagonistic contact; P4 = fully erupted and full occlusion.

Outcome Variable:

These data are doubly censored: neither the exact date of tooth emergence nor the moment at which a caries lesion fulfilled the clinical criteria for being diagnosed as caries is exactly known. As it has been demonstrated that in case of censored data a midpoint approach may lead to invalid inferences [Parner et al., 2001], [30] we opted not to compute point estimates, but to enter timing of emergence and caries experience as interval-censored data in the analyses. Based on the clinical eruption stage at the moment of examination, the left side of the time interval during which the permanent first molar had pierced the gums was approximated for every permanent first molar: The survival time of a permanent first molar was defined as the time from tooth emergence to the time when a permanent first molar was recorded as decayed, restored or extracted because of caries.

P1: [age at examination minus 0.25 year; age at examination];

P2: [age at examination minus 0.50 year; age at

examination];

P3: [age at examination minus 1.00 year;age at examination];

P4: [5 years old;age at examination].

Explanatory variables:

The presence of sealants on the occlusal surfaces of the permanent first molars was also taken into account. The choice of explanatory variables was based on the results of a previous study in the same sample [Leroy et al., 2004][29] where multiple survival analyses revealed that the state of the deciduous dentition, occlusal plaque accumulation, reported brushing frequency and gender had a significant effect on cavity formation in permanent first molars. At the examination where the presence of the permanent first molar was first recorded, the state of the adjacent primary molars was assessed; this score was used as explanatory variable.

Data Analysis:

The data (Clinical and questionnaire) was entered directly in a data base using the Dental Survey Plus® Program, version 4.50 b (Providence Software) and converted into SAS® files (version 8.2) for statistical analyses [SAS, 2002].[13]

RESULTS:

A statistically significant gender difference in caries experience was recorded for both mandibles first primary molars, these teeth were more frequently scored as cavity-free in girls than in boys. The state of primary molars (n = 2,252 boys and 2,111 girls) as observed at the examination where the presence of the permanent first molars was first recorded. The percentage sound primary molars ranged between 66 and 80;11–17% were decayed whereas 8–14% had been restored. Only 1–4% of primary molars were recorded as extracted because of (extensive) caries. Permanent first molars with a caries history at the first examination – i.e. 3–6% of the sample – were excluded from the present study. The proportion of sound permanent first molars dropped in the final survey year to 76% in girls and 79% in boys. Girls tended to have more affected permanent first molars than boys, the gender difference being statistically significant for the mandibular molars. On the other hand, the proportion of sealed permanent first molars was slightly higher in girls (i.e. 23%) than in boys (i.e. 21%).

Table 1 summarizes the acceleration factors corrected for all other included covariates.

Covariates	Overall p value ^a	Tooth 16		Tooth 26		Tooth 36		Tooth 46	
		acceleration factor ^b	95% CI						
Gender	0.060								
Male (reference)									
Female		0.92	0.84–1.01	0.94	0.86–1.03	0.87	0.79–0.96	0.87	0.78–0.96
Brushing frequency	<0.001								
Not daily (reference)									
Daily		1.29	1.14–1.45	1.31	1.15–1.49	1.42	1.25–1.60	1.36	1.19–1.54
Occlusal plaque	<0.001								
None (reference)									
In pits and fissures		0.93	0.84–1.03	0.85	0.77–0.95	0.82	0.73–0.91	0.84	0.75–0.95
On total occlusal surface		0.58	0.46–0.73	0.50	0.36–0.68	0.62	0.43–0.88	0.54	0.41–0.71
Pit and fissure sealing	<0.001								
None (reference)									
Present		1.39	1.25–1.56	1.41	1.25–1.59	1.23	1.10–1.38	1.14	1.02–1.28
Emergence interval	0.784								
[...–6] years (reference)									
[6–7] years		1.02	0.88–1.17	1.01	0.79–1.29	1.02	0.84–1.24	0.98	0.79–1.20
[7–...] years		1.00	0.82–1.20	1.01	0.84–1.22	0.93	0.77–1.12	0.86	0.71–1.05
Status first primary molar	<0.001								
Sound (reference)									
Decayed		0.81	0.70–0.94	0.77	0.65–0.91	0.86	0.75–0.99	0.80	0.69–0.93
Filled		0.79	0.68–0.93	0.88	0.73–1.05	0.72	0.62–0.84	0.73	0.63–0.86
Extracted		0.75	0.57–1.00	0.89	0.57–1.37	0.78	0.60–1.02	0.75	0.59–0.95
Status second primary molar	<0.001								
Sound (reference)									
Decayed		0.63	0.55–0.73	0.62	0.52–0.73	0.54	0.46–0.63	0.58	0.49–0.68
Filled		0.55	0.48–0.64	0.55	0.47–0.65	0.65	0.56–0.75	0.59	0.51–0.69
Extracted		0.66	0.43–1.00	0.55	0.32–0.94	0.37	0.28–0.51	0.44	0.31–0.61

^a p value for the overall impact of each (multicategorical) covariate over the first permanent molars.
^b An acceleration factor >1 indicates later visible caries experience. Italicized acceleration factors indicate statistically significant results.

Additional analyses evaluating the relationship between the period of time from caries occurrence to restoration in a deciduous molar and cavity formation in the adjacent permanent first molar revealed a possible but very weak correlation between both

survival curves; Kendall's Tau ranged between –0.08 and 0.14. children who reported frequent brushing, had their permanent first molars sealed and presented without occlusal plaque, a slightly increasing instantaneous risk over time is recorded. For

infrequent brushers who did present with visible plaque accumulation and no sealant on the occlusal surface of the permanent first molar and who experienced caries in both primary molars. Thereafter, the instantaneous risk decreases over time. Multiple survival analyses revealed that caries experience in deciduous molars as well as occlusal plaque accumulation on permanent first molars and reported brushing frequency had a significant impact on the incidence of visible caries experience in permanent first molars. An affected second primary molar had more effect than a first primary molar. In this sample only 1–3% of sealed permanent first molars developed caries (results not presented) the preventive effect of pit and fissure sealants – even after controlling for the other influencing factors – was statistically significant. The analyses revealed also that girls were more susceptible to caries development; this gender effect was only significant for mandibular molars. The effect of the emergence interval was not significant, indicating that after controlling for the other evaluated covariates – the effect of early versus late emergence is negligible when tooth emergence was taken as the zero-point of the survival analysis.

DISCUSSION:

No significant benefit from restoring primary molars could be demonstrated, possibly because of the methodological limitations of this study, therefore further research is indicated to fully explore this issue. In previous reports dealing with the correlation between caries prevalence in the primary and caries development in the permanent dentition [Poulsen and Holm, 1980; [14] ter Pelkwijk *et al.*, 1990; [15] Gray *et al.*, 1991; [10] Raadal and Espelid, 1992; [4] Li and Wang, 2002; [9] the relationship was expressed by sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive values. Based on high positive predictive values and sensitivity individuals can be selected who will benefit from preventive strategies (e.g. pit and fissure sealants), while high negative predictive values and specificity will help select those children where extra preventive efforts are redundant. However, one must realize that positive and negative predictive values are dependent on the prevalence of the predictor (i.e. caries experience in the primary dentition). In a population with low caries prevalence in the deciduous dentition, the positive predictive values are low and the negative predictive values high, while the opposite is observed in populations with a high dmft [Raadal and Espelid, 1992]. [4] In the present study survival analysis was applied to estimate the incidence of visible caries experience of the permanent first molars, the caries state of the

primary molars was – among other factors – added as covariate to the model. The advantages of survival analysis for the analysis of longitudinal caries data have been emphasized in recent reports [Hannigan *et al.*, 2000; [16] Baelum *et al.*, 2003; [17] it can estimate the time at risk for each individual tooth, even in case of censoring, and it allows for the altered number of teeth at risk, which is a result of the natural exfoliation and emergence process in 6- to 12-year-old children. In line with previous studies [Heidmann and Poulsen, 1986; [2] Greenwell *et al.*, 1990; [3] Mejåre *et al.*, 2001; [7] the analyses revealed that permanent molars adjacent to sound primary molars were less susceptible to caries development. As common risk factors such as dietary and oral hygiene habits are responsible for caries lesions in the primary as well as in the permanent dentition, these results were anticipated. On the other hand, even after controlling for common risk factors (i.e. occlusal plaque accumulation, reported brushing frequency, gender and presence of dental sealants), the effect of caries experience in the deciduous molars was significant, indicating a direct effect on cavity formation in the permanent first molars. Moreover, the greater impact of a carious second deciduous molar than of a carious first deciduous molar may indicate that the closer location of the former may have an additional effect on the caries development in the permanent first molar. Since only 1–4% of primary molars in this sample had been extracted because of caries, no useful conclusions could be drawn from this subgroup.

Unexpectedly, only a small and non consistent advantage of restoring an affected deciduous primary molar on the incidence of visible caries experience in the adjacent permanent first molar was observed. Mejåre *et al.* [2001]; [7] similarly found no benefit from restoring the lesion in the deciduous molar with amalgam as opposed to leaving the lesion unrestored. They suggested that the outcome might have been different if a fluoride-releasing filling material had been used. As in the present survey clinical examinations were not performed in connection with routine dental treatment appointments, no information was available regarding the applied restorative material. Hence, the influence of the nature of the filling material could not be evaluated.

Mejåre *et al.* [2001]; [7] indicated also that the lack of effectiveness of restoring the deciduous molar may be ascribed to possible preparation damage during cavity preparation. In the present sample – as in reports from other industrialized countries [Ripa *et al.*, 1985]; [18] – the majority of caries experience in the

permanent first molars was limited to the occlusal surfaces, so this hypothesis can explain the results only in part. Since the examinations in the present survey were performed on a yearly basis and not in connection with dental treatment appointments, no detailed information on the occurrence of the carious lesion or on the length of time between caries occurrence and restoration was available. Hence, a primary molar could have been decayed for only a couple of months when the tooth was scored or affected for a long time and filled just before the examination. Additional analyses revealed a possible but very weak correlation between the period of time from caries occurrence to restoration in a deciduous molar and the incidence of visible caries experience in the adjacent permanent first molar.

A strong negative correlation would have indicated that when a primary molar was decayed for a long time before being restored the adjacent permanent first molar had a higher chance of being affected by caries whereas a permanent first molar adjacent to a primary molar that had been restored shortly after caries experience would be less susceptible to caries experience. Although Levine et al. [2002],[19] reported that 74% of unrestored carious deciduous teeth were exfoliated without causing pain, further follow-up studies are indicated to fully evaluate the benefits from restoring primary teeth since untreated carious lesions may act as a source of pathogenic flora for erupting permanent teeth.

The influence of fissure sealants was also evaluated. In spite of their technique-dependent durability, fissure sealants had – even after controlling for other influencing factors – a statistically significant caries-preventive effect [Ahovuo-Saloranta et al., 2004]. [20]

Dental sealants for instance have most likely no caries-preventive effect on proximal surfaces, the presence of occlusal plaque may only have a cariogenic effect on the occlusal surfaces, although regarded as a parameter of oral hygiene efficiency, it may well be associated with caries susceptibility of the proximal surfaces. In earlier longitudinal caries studies it was reported that caries risk of permanent first molars was highest 1–4 years after emergence and decreased thereafter [Carlos and Gittelsohn, 1965.[21] Abernathy et al., 1986],[22] while more recently the absence of a peak in caries susceptibility was recorded [Ripa et al., 1988;[23] Suni et al., 1998;[27] Harkanen et al., 2002;[24] Seppä et al., 2002;[25] Leroy et al., 2004].[26] however, give evidence for both – seemingly contradictory – results. They illustrate a peak in (instantaneous) caries risk

1–2 years after emergence in infrequent brushers who did present with dental plaque on the occlusal surface and who had experienced caries in the adjacent primary molars, while children who reported frequent brushing and presented without occlusal plaque, experienced a slightly increasing instantaneous risk over time. The curves confirm that cavity formation in permanent molars is dependent on oral hygiene, the application of dental sealants and visible caries experience of the adjacent primary molars. Although ‘statistical risk’ should not be confused with ‘clinical risk’, the results indicate that there is no maximum age for preventive efforts. The results are in line with a longitudinal Dutch study where it was concluded that at the age of 17 occlusal surfaces of permanent molars are still highly susceptible to new dentine caries and further progression of dental radiolucencies already present [Poorterman et al., 2003]. [28] In conclusion, cavity formation in permanent first molars is influenced by the status of the adjacent primary molars, especially the second deciduous molar. If both deciduous molars had experienced caries and the child presented with poor oral hygiene, a peak in caries susceptibility 1–2 years after emergence of the permanent first molar was noticed. On the other hand, if a child reported good oral hygiene, caries risk increased slightly over time.

Further research is indicated to explore the impact of reported brushing frequency, presence of occlusal sealants, presence of occlusal plaque and caries experience in the primary dentition on caries development at surface level.

CONCLUSION:

Child who has a good oral hygiene status in the primary dentition, caries exposure gets minimized, and caries risks also decreases. Overall mandibular teeth have more caries when compared to maxillary. Only 10% of the sample did not have caries in a permanent first molar. Parental awareness is less regarding their child's dentition status. Thus, the community-based awareness program has to be conducted to emphasize paediatric oral health status and care.

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